

ADJUSTMENT OF ADOLESCENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER AND RESIDENTIAL BACKGROUND

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Abstract

This study was conducted to examine the impact of gender and residential background on adjustment of adolescents. A sample of 1200 male and female adolescents was randomly taken from government and private schools located in rural and urban areas of Himachal Pradesh. Data was collected by using Adjustment Inventory developed by Prof. A.K.P. Sinha and Prof. R.P. Singh (2019). The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The findings of the study revealed that there is no significant difference in adjustment of adolescents with respect to gender but students from urban and rural area shows significant difference in their adjustments. The study revealed that adolescents from urban area are more adjusted as comparison to adolescents of rural area.

Keywords: *Adjustment of Adolescents, Gender and Residential Background*

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INTRODUCTION

Education is a comprehensive, inclusive process that helps people to make changes psychologically and behaviorally. It plays role of transformative as it fosters adaptability and change in such a way that helps individuals to develop harmoniously flexible personality. Every

state of life requires that every individual should be able to act effectively in accordance with some guiding principles and should be able to balance a variety of forces. It supports the control of fundamental urges to manageable levels, self-belief, and goal achievement. Psychologically, adjustment aids the individual's ability to manage its needs, desires, and internal conflicts in addition to the pressures and expectations of the outside world. Therefore, adjustment supports self-initiated development in the areas of intellectual, emotional, social, physical, and vocational growth. Improper adjustment not only disturbs their normal growth but as well as disturbs their academic progress. It is a well-established truth that a child's ability to make adjustments to school and their academic success are immensely influenced by a range of personal, family, and societal factors. Adjustment in a fast-changing world is an important socio-psychological aspect to be studied constantly. The problem of adjustment demands more consideration particularly during the most critical period 'adolescence' and old age. Hence the process of adjustment is becoming more and more complex and stress full. Twenty-first century is a time of revolutionary change, and in order to adapt to and survive in such a dynamic environment, one must transform either their surroundings or themselves. If the person does not adapt to the changing times and transform himself, he will eventually give in to the pressures of his surroundings. "Adjustment is the outcome of the individual's attempt to deal with the stress and meet his needs, as well as his efforts to maintain harmonious relationship with the environment," according to James C. Coleman. Adjustment among adolescents has been studied by a number of researchers. Some researchers found that adjustment is more widespread in case of adolescents (Kaur, 2012; Basu, 2012; Rajeshwari, 2013; Vishal, 2014; Devika, 2014; Parmar, 2014; Makwana, 2014; Mehmood, 2015; Gul et. al., 2015; Pooja, 2016; Sekar, 2016; Bhakta, 2016; Chamyal, 2017; Packiasely, 2017; Usha, 2018; Bimla, 2019; Barik, 2019; Vyas, 2021; Kaur et. al., 2021; D'Souza, 2022; Kaur, 2022). Opposing to that (Emmanuel, 2013; Nidhi, 2015) found that gender is not only significantly related to adjustment. It was observed that the main factors that lead to adjustment among adolescents are gender, type of school and residential background (Gupta, P. (2021); Wadhawan, 2018). Adjustment has been investigated in relation to residential background (Deepsikha et.al.,2011; Punia, 2011; Kaur, 2012; Rajeshwari, 2013; Okorodudu, 2013; Parmar, 2014; Sekar, 2016; Bhakta, 2016; Chamyal, 2017; Packiasely, 2017; Srivastva,2018; Wadhwan, 2018; Kour,2019; Bimla, 2019; Babasaheb,2019). Some researchers (Muthukumar, 2015; Sherifat et. al, 2016; Bhakta, 2016; Birano, 2017; Usha, 2018; Mathew, 2019; Janardhan, 2020;

Bhardwaj, 2021; Kaur, 2021) found a no relation between adjustment and residential background.

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY: The behavioral mechanism that keeps people and other animals in balance between their requirements and their surroundings. Adjustment is the process of making changes that starts when a need is identified and ends when it is fulfilled. When requirements arise, particularly in unfamiliar or altered environments, they motivate interpersonal engagement designed to meet those requirements. People get more comfortable to and at ease in their surroundings in this way, and they start to anticipate that their social networks will take care of their needs in future as well. Adolescence is an intermediate period of human life when numerous bodily and psychological fluctuations are taking place. Adolescents who are also identified as youngsters, infants, young people, form a discrete population cluster in humanity because of their exceptional genetic, psychological and communal features. During this period adolescent's effort to fine-tune their conduct, attitude according to the requirement of the humanity. The youth in this period starts thinking in different way. They like to being self-governing of the family members, start friendships with their peers and create their own trust and attitude. To deal with these fluctuations and to regulate and achieve successfully in the humanity life skills education play an important role in every adolescent's life during their adolescence phase. Life skill education is a sequencer of instruction the fundamental life skills in an effective teaching-learning setting. The key objective of the life skills education program is to make students efficient to take precise decisions that help them to live a fruitful life. Life skills education allow people to recognize themselves as well as assess their strengths, weakness and progress level. It helps youth to conduct efficiently in the humanity and to make adjustment with the fluctuating environment and allows them to make accountable choices. Life skills help adolescents to make improvement in their lives. In life skills education program basic skills building activities are taught through group discussion, brain storming, role play etc. These life skills help an adolescent to overcome problems they face in their life. By acquiring these skills young people learn to interact with others in the society. It helps them to control their feelings and take right decisions whenever needed.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the adjustment of adolescents in relation to their gender.
2. To study the adjustment of adolescents in relation to their residential background.

HYPOTHESES

1. There will be no significant difference in adjustment of adolescents in relation to their gender.
2. There will be no significant difference in adjustment of adolescents in relation to their residential background.

METHODOLOGY

This study applied survey methods due to its descriptive nature.

- **Sample:** The present study was carried out on 1200 adolescents ranged from 12 to 18 years belonging to four districts (Mandi, Shimla, Kangra, Sirmour) of Himachal Pradesh. The sample was randomly selected from government and private schools located in rural and urban areas of mentioned districts.
- **Tool used:** The investigator used Adjustment Inventory developed by Prof. A.K.P. Sinha and Prof. R.P. Singh (2019) for data collection. The inventory measures the adjustment of adolescents in three areas of adjustment - emotional, social and educational. The inventory comprises of total 60 items.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE DATA: Descriptive statistics were computed and the inferential statistics (t-test) was employed to compare the means of the students across said variable.

1. **Adjustment of Adolescents with respect to Gender:** The first objective was to study the adjustment of adolescents in relation to their gender. To explore the difference in adjustment of adolescents with respect to gender, the adjustment scores of the male and female adolescents were calculated and t-test was employed to analyze the difference. The results so obtained have been presented in Table 1.

Table-1: 't' Value Showing Significance of Difference in Mean Scores of 'Adjustments' of adolescents in relation to Gender

Sr. No.	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value
1.	Male	600	55.05	10.680	0.138 NS
2.	Female	600	54.97	10.211	

Table 1 revealed that mean and standard deviation (SD) of adjustment scores of the male students are 55.05 and 10.680 respectively, whereas the mean and standard deviation (SD) of the adjustment scores of the female students are 54.97 and 10.211 respectively. The calculated t-value turned out to be 0.138 and it is not significant even at 0.05 level. This revealed that there

exists no significant difference in adjustment of male and female adolescents and they possess almost equal adjustment (emotional, social and educational).

2. **Adjustment of Adolescents with respect to Residential Background:** The second objective of the study was to explore the difference in adjustment of adolescents with respect to their residential background. It was hypothesized that there is no significant difference in the adjustment of adolescents with respect to rural and urban locality. To verify this hypothesis, mean scores on adjustment of the adolescents with respect to their residential background were calculated and t-test was employed to analyze the further difference. The results so obtained have been presented in Table 2.

Table-2: 't' Value Showing Significance of Difference in Mean Scores of 'Adjustments' of adolescents in relation to Residential Background

Sr. No.	Residential Background	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value
1.	Rural	600	53.92	10.316	3.628*
2.	Urban	600	56.10	10.466	

*** Significant at 0.05 level**

Table 2 reveals that mean and standard deviation (SD) of adjustment scores of the students studying in rural areas are 53.92 and 10.316 respectively, whereas the mean and standard deviation (SD) of the adjustment scores of the students studying in urban are 56.10 and 10.466 respectively. The calculated t-value turned out to be 3.628 and it is significant at 0.05 level of significance. This value shows that a significant difference exists in adjustment of adolescents studying in schools located in rural and urban areas. Hence, the hypothesis "There will be no significant difference in adjustment of adolescents in relation to their residential background" was rejected. It means the adolescents studying in schools located in rural and urban areas differ significantly with respect to their residential background.

As the mean scores (56.10) on adjustment of adolescents studying in urban areas were found to be higher than the mean scores (53.92) on adjustment of adolescents studying in rural areas. It may be further concluded that the adolescents studying in urban areas are better adjusted than the adolescents studying in rural areas. The significant difference was shown in figure-1.

Figure-1: Difference in Mean Scores of 'Adjustments' of adolescents in relation to Residential Background

CONCLUSIONS: On the basis of findings, it may be concluded that significant difference was found in adjustment of adolescents with respect to the residential background. Academicians, legislators, families, and all other relevant stakeholders must take priority in developing strategies to help adolescents to develop better adjusting skills. Adolescence is a very critical stage in adolescents lives where they are still figuring out who they are and what their purpose in society. They are most in need of their ability to adjust at this critical phase of their lives. A strategy should be developed by all the involved stakeholders to minimize discrepancies resulting from different demographic factors and to improve adjustment skills. To satisfy their demands, the following activities need to be completed:

1. Families need to foster an atmosphere where adolescents feel free to voice their opinions. Parents must also provide equal care for boys and girls.
2. The school must plan NCC/NSS events that foster the development of positive social skills like cooperation and consideration, which act as aid in their ability to adjust.
3. Students ought to have the chance to voice their own opinions and ideas to discuss their issues with parents and teachers.
4. There is a need of guidance and counseling cell for each school which serve to assist students in coping and adjusting to school and social life.

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